

DEVELOPMENT OF INCLUSIVE COMPETENCE IN FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

Jorayeva Mushtari Mukhaydinovna

KIUT Tashkent International University of Chemistry

Namangan Branch Teacher of Pedagogy Department

Abstract: In this article, inclusive education, its content, and the activity of providing knowledge to children who are brought up in this type of education are highlighted. At the same time, the inclusive educational environment and its requirements for pedagogues and the essence of inclusive pedagogical competence were discussed.

Key words: Inclusive education, theory and technology of inclusive education, inclusion, integration, social integration, competence, dialogical nature.

For every country and state, the education of the young generation of this country is today's step towards the future, providing them with knowledge in accordance with the educational standards that meet modern requirements. It is necessary for every teacher to fully study all the conditions and conditions necessary for working with children with learning disabilities. Despite the fact that this field of education is new in the field of education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the work carried out in our country on the education of children with disabilities is reflected in the activities carried out in cooperation with the world organization for the protection of children, UNICEF. Countries with developed inclusive education on a global scale and the results of research conducted in this field remain the most pressing issue of the day in the education of children with physical disabilities in inclusive education. This, in turn, requires a special plan and programmed complex research.

Inclusive education is a certain innovation for the local education system,

so it requires competent management at all stages of its modeling and implementation. The effectiveness of inclusive education includes the creation of a number of conditions, the main ones of which are:

1. The readiness of specialists to implement the inclusive pedagogical process (includes all types of preparation: - personal, professional, psychological, etc.),

2. Humanitarian education system, including formation of moral and psychological environment in the community; - organization of correctional support and psychological pedagogical support for the development and socialization of children.

A master's degree prepared in the direction of "Psychological Pedagogical Education" can become a coordinator in the field of supporting the socialization of children in the conditions of inclusion, ensuring the implementation of the mechanisms of effective functioning of inclusive conditions and parameters. Therefore, it is necessary to acquire knowledge, skills, and abilities that will allow to successfully solve the problems of supporting inclusive education subjects in the process of personnel training at the bachelor's and master's level. Currently, the course "Theory and Technology of Inclusive Education" has been established, which involves introducing students to the innovative practical psychological field, providing students with an understanding of the essence and methods of implementation of inclusive pedagogy, the theory and understanding of the practice of pedagogical activity in the conditions of educational inclusion. helps to develop, develops creative abilities. The purpose of the course is to develop students' understanding of the theoretical foundations and practical mechanisms of building an inclusive educational environment. In inclusive education, it consists in the formation of competencies that ensure solving the problems of monitoring the child, the teacher, and the family.

In modern science and practice, terms such as integration, mainstreaming, and inclusion are used to define and describe the pedagogical process of joint education and upbringing of healthy children and disabled children. The term "integration" comes from the Latin word *integrare* - to fill, to fill.

The term "social integration" appeared in pedagogy in the 20th century. and was first used in the United States from the 60s of the 20th century in relation to the problems of racial and ethnic minorities. This term entered the discourse in Europe and began to be used in the context of the problems of the disabled. The concept of mainstreaming (in English *mainstream*, that is, alignment, reduction to a common pattern) in foreign literature refers to the strategy of students with disabilities to communicate with their peers within the framework of various free time programs, which allows them to expand their social contacts. As a rule, no educational goals are set here. Inclusive education is a term used to describe the process of teaching children with special needs in general education (public) schools. Inclusive education is education that gives every child the opportunity to join the general (unified, integrated) process of education and upbringing (development and socialization), despite the existing physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic and other characteristics. and allows the growing person to become an equal member of society, reduces the risk of separation and isolation. In general, inclusive education is the process of developing general education, which implies the availability of education for all, which ensures the opportunity for children with special needs to receive education. The concept of "inclusive education" (French *inclusif*) is relatively new for our country (it was used in the late 90s). Federal Law No. 273-FZ of December 29, 2012 "On Education in the Russian Federation" (Article 2) defines inclusive education as education for all students, taking into account the diversity of special educational needs. defined as ensuring equal access. individual capabilities. The practice of inclusion became possible due to the spread of ideas and principles of normalization in society. The

concept of normalization was formed in Europe in the 1960s, according to its ideas, every person is valuable, regardless of what kind of person he is and what success he can achieve; all people have the right to a decent human life; society should create such opportunities for everyone, which shows the need to provide education opportunities for all categories of children, to include specialized correctional pedagogical support for children who need special education. The term "inclusive education" is more modern and reflective. The new vision is not only about the education system, but also about the place of a person in society. Inclusion involves solving the problem of teaching disabled children by adapting the educational space, reforming the school environment to the needs of each child, including the educational process, (redesigning classrooms to meet the needs and requirements of all children without exception planning, necessary instructional manuals according to the type of developmental deviation of the child, psychological and methodological preparation of teachers, etc.). Thus, inclusion refers to the inclusion of children with special educational needs in public institutions, where it is important to remove all barriers to the full participation of each child in the educational process.

The dialogic nature of pedagogical interactions allows the child to be himself and opens the way for him to trust himself, his inner world and the other world, and not see himself and others through the prism of inferiority. man Achieving confidence is the basis of a life-affirming human strategy, and its foundation is laid through childhood experiences. Inclusive competence of the pedagogue Here, pedagogues engaged in inclusive activities allow professional culture, communication with the surrounding world, development of your abilities, self-realization and success (Khutorskoy A.V., Starova N.M.). Competence is a measure of the actualization of competencies related to the self-activation of a graduate in the relevant activity during their development (Subetto

A.I.).

From the point of view of competence-based approach to professional pedagogical activity, many studies make sure that it has become an integral part of it. Competency-based approach makes a great impression as it is considered as the foundation of the changes implemented in the educational system, as a resource for the qualitative development of professional skills and the quality of education in general. The implementation of inclusive practice is related to the distribution and meaningful description of the teacher's competence as a set of personal and professional qualities that are clearly realized in the innovative conditions of the inclusive environment, which allows him to successfully solve problems related to the organization of teaching. will give. It is necessary to educate and educate all children, without exception, taking into account the specific characteristics of their educational needs. The interdependence of the level of the teacher's professional activity as a subject of educational practice and a child's self-development has been proven in acmeology for a long time. The teacher's competences serve as a means and condition for the development of the competences of his students.

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